

Positive Effects of Neuro Soundwave to Improve Sleep Quality

Tang Juel Hoi, Tang Yu Zhun

Neuro Code Research Centre, Neuro Code Research Pte Ltd

ABSTRACT

Sleep is an important and integral part of our life. We spend about 1/3 of our life sleeping. It is as essential as having sufficient food and water to sustain our body. With the rapid increase of high technology gadgets around us, our brains are being subjected to high levels of stimulation and increasingly more difficult to get into a restful state. Research efforts into non-pharmacological solutions to improve sleep quality led to the development of Neuro Soundwave.

The focus of research was to develop a Soundwave pattern with specific frequencies and amplitudes that could bring the stressful and restless mind to a calm and relaxed state. Neuro Soundwave also induces micro-oscillations around pineal gland region to promote production of melatonin that could lead to drowsiness and sleepiness of the participants.

A clinical trial of 100 participants conducted over a period of one month provided positive results to participants facing sleep disorders. It also helped to prolong the duration of deep sleep (delta state) that aids the production of human growth hormone (HGH) for cell repairs and immune system build-up. The results also showed an improvement in prolonging the REM cycle that could improve the participants' memory.

THE SCIENCE OF SLEEP

Sleep is an important part of our daily routine. We spend about 1/3 of our life sleeping. A recent study found that for every hour of active learning, our brain requires about 30 mins in our sleep to consolidate and store the information in a stable form of memory. This provides a clue as to why we need to sleep 8 hours a day for 16 hours of waking time.

The value of sleep does not lie in the total duration of sleep. Rather, it lies in the quality of sleep. Getting enough quality sleep every day is as essential to survival as getting enough food and water for our body. Without sleep we cannot form or maintain the pathways in our brain that let us learn and create new memories, and it is harder to concentrate and respond quickly.

There are 3 Key reasons that we must have good quality sleep each night in order to stay in good physical and mental health. Quality sleep is not just about the duration of sleep, it also includes the depth of sleep and the duration of REM cycles. Many research findings suggest that sleep plays a housekeeping role by removing toxins in our brain that build up while you are awake. This is an essential process that happens daily in our sleep to ensure all chemical byproducts are cleansed from our brain.

The second reason that we need to have enough time of deep sleep (delta state), is that during deep sleep our brains secrete human growth hormones (HGH) for our body tissues to repair itself and strengthening our immune system. Research also shows that a chronic lack of sleep, or getting poor quality sleep, increases the risk of disorders including high blood pressure, cardiovascular disease, diabetes, depression, and obesity. It is a basic but necessary routine that we must keep to ensure an active and healthy mind.

Everyone needs sleep, but its biological purpose remains a mystery. Sleep affects almost every type of tissue and system in the body - from the brain, heart, and lungs to metabolism, immune function, mood, and disease resistance.

The third reason to have quality sleep is to ensure our brains have sufficient time to process the information acquired during waking hours, packaging and storing them a stable form of memory; predominantly in the Amygdala and Cerebral Cortex. This process of stable memory creation by our brain happens actively in the REM cycle.

Sleep and wakefulness are generally regulated by our brains working with input from our senses and our circadian clock. Our body has a natural clock, called a “circadian clock,” that helps us to regulate our sleep. The word “circadian” refers to rhythmic biological cycles that repeat about every 24 hours. These cycles are also called circadian rhythms. Our circadian clock is strongly influenced by light, which is the reason why people living in different regions have different sleeping schedules. This is also the reason why people who work night shifts can have difficulty falling asleep or staying awake.

At bedtime, when our drive to sleep is greatest, our sleep drive and circadian clock work together to allow us to fall asleep. After we have slept for some time, when our drive to sleep is lower, our circadian clock allows us to stay asleep until the end of the night.

Circadian rhythms regulate changes in the brain and body that occur over the course of a day. Our body’s biological clock controls most circadian rhythms. This clock is found in a region of the brain called the hypothalamus. The hypothalamus affects sleep and arousal.

Light detected by special neurons in the eye sends signals to many areas of the brain, including the hypothalamus. Signals from the hypothalamus travel to different regions of the brain, including the pineal gland. In response to light, such as sunlight, the pineal gland turns off the production of melatonin, a hormone that causes a feeling of drowsiness. The levels of melatonin in the body normally increase after darkness, which makes you feel drowsy.

The change in melatonin during the sleep/wake cycle reflects circadian rhythms. During sleep, the hypothalamus also controls changes in body temperature and blood pressure.

Because circadian rhythms are controlled by light, people who have some degree of blindness in both eyes may have trouble sleeping.

PARTS OF BRAIN THAT INVOLVE IN SLEEP

Several structures within the brain are involved with sleep.

The **hypothalamus**, a peanut-sized structure deep inside the brain, contains groups of nerve cells that act as control centres affecting sleep and arousal. Within the hypothalamus is the **suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN)** – clusters of thousands of cells that receive information about light exposure directly from the eyes and control your behavioural rhythm. Some people with damage to the SCN sleep erratically throughout the day because they are not able to match their circadian rhythms with the light-dark cycle. Most blind people maintain some ability to sense light and are able to modify their sleep/wake cycle.

The **brain stem**, at the base of the brain, communicates with the hypothalamus to control the transitions between wake and sleep. (The brain stem includes structures called the pons, medulla, and midbrain.) Sleep-promoting cells within the hypothalamus and the brain stem produce a brain chemical called *GABA*, which acts to reduce the activity of arousal centres in the hypothalamus and the brain stem. The brain stem (especially the pons and medulla) also plays a special role in REM sleep; it sends signals to relax muscles essential for body posture and limb movements, so that we don’t act out our dreams.

The **thalamus** acts as a relay for information from the senses to the **cerebral cortex** (the covering of the brain that interprets and processes information from short- to long-term memory). During most stages of sleep, the thalamus

becomes quiet, letting you tune out the external world. But during REM sleep, the thalamus is active, sending the cortex images, sounds, and other sensations that fill our dreams.

The **pineal gland**, located within the brain's two hemispheres, receives signals from the SCN and increases production of the hormone *melatonin*, which helps put you to sleep once the lights go down. People who have lost their sight and cannot coordinate their natural wake-sleep cycle using natural light can stabilize their sleep patterns by taking small amounts of melatonin at the same time each day. Scientists believe that peaks and valleys of melatonin over time are important for matching the body's circadian rhythm to the external cycle of light and darkness.

The **basal forebrain**, near the front and bottom of the brain, also promotes sleep and wakefulness, while part of the **midbrain** acts as an arousal system. Release of adenosine (a chemical by-product of cellular energy consumption) from cells in the basal forebrain and probably other regions supports your sleep drive. Caffeine counteracts sleepiness by blocking the actions of adenosine.

The **amygdala**, an almond-shaped structure involved in processing emotions, becomes increasingly active during REM sleep.

THE MECHANISM OF SLEEP

Two internal biological mechanisms: circadian rhythm and homeostasis, work together to regulate when we are awake and asleep.

Circadian rhythms direct a wide variety of functions from daily fluctuations in wakefulness to body temperature, metabolism, and the release of hormones. They control our timing of sleep and cause us to be sleepy at night and our tendency to wake in the morning without an alarm. Our body's biological clock, which is based on a roughly 24-hour day, controls most circadian rhythms. Circadian rhythms synchronize with environmental cues (light, temperature) about the actual time of day, but they continue even in the absence of cues.

Our body's biological clock is based on a 24-hour day and controls most circadian rhythms. These rhythms affect a variety of functions including body temperature (represented as the white line on the chart above). Melatonin - a hormone released by the pineal gland - helps us feel sleepy once the lights go down. The peaks and valleys of melatonin (represented as the gold line above) are important for matching the body's circadian rhythm to the external cycle of light and darkness.

Sleep-wake homeostasis keeps track of our need for sleep. The homeostatic sleep drive reminds the body to sleep after a certain time and regulates sleep intensity. This sleep drive gets stronger every hour we are awake and causes us to sleep longer and more deeply after a period of sleep deprivation.

Factors that influence our sleep-wake needs include medical conditions, medications, stress, sleep environment, and what you eat and drink. Perhaps the greatest influence is the exposure to light. Specialised cells in the retinas of your eyes process light and tell the brain whether it is day or night and can advance or delay our sleep-wake cycle. Exposure to light can make it difficult to fall asleep and return to sleep when awakened.

THE CHALLENGES OF SLEEP IN MODERN SOCIETY

A global sleep survey (across 12 countries) conducted by Philips and KJT Group in 2019 found that 62% of adults don't feel that they get enough sleep; and most were not getting the recommended 8 hours each night. Adults clocked an average of 6.8 hours of sleep on weekdays, while on weekends it was 7.8 hours. As a comparison, people slept an average of 9 hours per night in 1910. Things also do not appear to be improving with time, as 44% also felt that their sleep has deteriorated over the past 5 years. 35% of people do not feel they get enough sleep, impacting both their physical and mental health.

In our research, we focus on two categories of population. The first group is people who have difficulty sleeping and suffer from poor sleep quality. The second group is people who do not have sufficient hours to sleep due to long hours spent in study, work, using mobile phones or playing games. These two groups are facing different sets of problems.

The first group has biological and physiological issues such as the pineal gland not producing sufficient melatonin, and a stressed and disturb mind. Stress and disturbance could come from work or life events. It could be affected by high technology equipment that produces high frequencies bringing our brains to a gamma state.

The second population group does not have sleep issues. However, their busy work or study schedule coupled with lifestyle could lead to having very few hours of sleep each night. The overall population's sleep hours are getting shorter as our society progresses and people are getting busier with their lives. For this category of population, our research focus is to optimise their sleep quality. The objective is to get quality sleep from 6 hours sleep that is equivalent to 8 hours of sleep. The key focus is on getting a longer duration of deep sleep and REM cycles.

BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF NEUROSOUNDWAVE

Clusters of sleep-promoting neurons in many parts of the brain become more active as we get ready for bed. Nerve-signaling chemicals called neurotransmitters can "switch off" or dampen the activity of cells that signal arousal or relaxation. Gamma-aminobutyric acid is associated with sleep, muscle relaxation, and sedation. Norepinephrine and orexin (also called hypocretin) keep some parts of the brain active while we are awake. Other neurotransmitters that shape sleep and wakefulness include acetylcholine, histamine, adrenaline, cortisol, and serotonin.

Neuro Soundwave embeds waves into music to be delivered to our brain via the cochlea. The cochlea is a fluid-filled, spiral-shaped cavity found in the inner ear that plays a vital role in the sense of hearing and participates in the process of auditory transduction. Soundwave are transduced into electrical impulses that the brain can interpret as individual sound frequencies. The spiral configuration of the cochlea allows for differing frequencies to stimulate specific areas along the spiral, which results in a tonotopic map that enables humans to perceive various frequencies of sound.

Soundwaves are produced in speakers by oscillating a cone, causing vibrations of air molecules. A speaker vibrates at a constant frequency and amplitude, producing vibrations in the surrounding air molecules. As the speaker oscillates back and forth, it transfers energy to the air, mostly as thermal energy. But a small part of the speaker's energy goes into compressing and expanding the surrounding air, creating slightly higher and lower local pressures. These compressions (high-pressure regions) and rarefactions (low-pressure regions) move out as longitudinal pressure waves having the same frequency as the speaker; they are the disturbance that is known as a soundwave. (Soundwaves in air and most fluids are longitudinal, because fluids have almost no shear strength. In solids, soundwaves can be both transverse and longitudinal.)

As the speaker moves in the positive x-direction, it pushes air molecules, displacing them from their equilibrium positions. As the speaker moves in the negative x-direction, the air molecules move back toward their equilibrium positions due to a restoring force. The air molecules oscillate in simple harmonic motion about their equilibrium positions. Note that soundwaves in air are longitudinal, and in the figure below, the wave propagates in the positive x-direction and the molecules oscillate parallel to the direction in which the wave propagates.

(a) A vibrating cone of a speaker, moving in the positive x-direction, compresses the air in front of it and expands the air behind it. As the speaker oscillates, it creates another compression and rarefaction as those on the right move away from the speaker. After many vibrations, a series of compressions and rarefactions moves out from the speaker as a sound wave. The red graph shows the gauge pressure of the air versus the distance from the speaker. Pressures vary only slightly from atmospheric pressure for ordinary sounds. Note that gauge pressure is modelled with a sine function, where the crests of the function line up with the compressions and the troughs line up with the rarefactions. (b) Soundwaves can also be modelled using the displacement of the air molecules.

The blue graph shows the displacement of the air molecules versus the position from the speaker and is modelled with a cosine function. Notice that the displacement is zero for the molecules in their equilibrium position and are centred at the compressions and rarefactions. Compressions are formed when molecules on either side of the equilibrium molecules are displaced toward the equilibrium position. Rarefactions are formed when the molecules are displaced away from the equilibrium position.

Sound can be modelled as a pressure wave by considering the change in pressure from average pressure

$$\Delta P = \Delta P_{\max} \sin(kx - \omega t + \phi)$$

This equation is similar to the periodic wave equations seen in Waves, where ΔP is the change in pressure, ΔP_{\max} is the maximum change in pressure, $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ is the wave number, $\omega = 2\pi/T = 2\pi f$ is the angular frequency, and ϕ is the initial phase. The wave speed can be determined from

$$v = \omega/k = \lambda T$$

Soundwaves can also be modelled in terms of the displacement of the air molecules. The displacement of the air molecules can be modelled using a cosine function:

$$s(x, t) = s_{\max} \cos(kx - \omega t + \phi)$$

In this equation, s is the displacement and s_{\max} is the maximum displacement.

Not shown in the figure is the amplitude of a soundwave as it decreases with distance from its source, because the energy of the wave is spread over a larger and larger area. The intensity decreases as it moves away from the speaker. The energy is also absorbed by objects and converted into thermal energy by the viscosity of the air. In addition, during each compression, a little heat transfers to the air; during each rarefaction, even less heat transfers from the air, and these heat transfers reduce the organized disturbance into random thermal motions. Whether the heat transfer from compression to rarefaction is significant depends on how far apart they are; that is, it depends on wavelength.

Wavelength, frequency, amplitude, and speed of propagation are important characteristics for sound, as they are for all waves.

EFFECT OF NEURO SOUNDWAVE ON SLEEP

A clinical trial conducted to test the effect of Neuro Soundwave on sleep challenges produced several positive effects. Among the 100 participants who took part in this clinical trial, 75% of them experienced improvements in their sleep quality after using Neuro Soundwave for 2-4 weeks. The trial used Withing Sleep Tracking Pad as a sleep quality measurement tool.

3 Key parameters were monitored during the one-month trial – (1) time to sleep, (2) duration of deep sleep and (3) duration of REM cycles. Among the participants, 75% experienced improvement in time needed to enter sleep, 83% experienced improvement in prolonged duration of deep sleep cycles and 83% experienced improvement in prolonged duration of REM cycles. The improvement in deep sleep cycles could lead to better health and stronger immune system of the participants. Improvement in REM cycles could be associated to improved memory of participants. The results are encouraging as they demonstrated positive effects of Neuro Soundwave on improving sleep quality.

Neuro Soundwave affects the brain in 2 aspects. The first aspect is to calm down the brain and relax it. A key technology deployed for sleep is the brain entrainment technology. Micro-oscillations of pre-defined frequencies and wave patterns were used to create a resonance effect in the brain. As time goes, the wave pattern gradually dropped its frequencies from Beta to Delta state. This induces a calm and relaxing effect in the brain which leads to falling asleep. Data is measured through the use of Electro-encephalogram (EEG) as show in the output images below. The EEG equipment measured the various frequencies of brainwaves and plotted them in categories of alpha, beta, theta, delta and gamma.

The general observation after a participant listens to Neuro Soundwave for 30mins is a decrease in amplitude at the higher frequency range of brainwaves. This is a relaxed state where participants start to feel calm and relax, as compared to the initial phase of high activity in the brain cells.

The second aspect focuses on the pineal gland. Specific frequencies and wave patterns were introduced to create micro-oscillations around the region of the pineal gland. This activity promotes the production of melatonin from the pineal gland which leads to drowsiness and sleepiness of the participant. Data collected showed positive effects in this aspect.

CONCLUDING COMMENTS

Extensive research was carried out by the Neuro Code Research Centre to establish the effect of Neuro Soundwave on improving sleep quality. The research conclusion found several positive effects of Neuro Soundwaves. It is able to reduce the higher frequency components in the subjects' brainwave patterns, leading to a calm and relaxed mind which helps participants to reduce their time needed to enter sleep. We also see a significant improvement of sleep quality with controlled frequencies and wave patterns to induce micro-oscillations around the pineal gland region. It promotes production of melatonin and helps participants to enter the initial stages of sleep. The clinical trial conducted showed the positive effects of Neuro Soundwave to improve sleep quality.

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